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WIND IN MY BACKYARD

WIMBY

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SHORT ABSTRACT FOR DISSEMINATION PURPOSES

Abstract

This report presents the development of novel open-source mapping tools designed to assess the noise, shadow flicker, and safety impacts of wind turbines on the population in Europe.

Concerning noise, the tool presented addresses the growing concern over wind turbine noise emissions and their compliance with World Health Organisation (WHO) guidelines. The tool leverages a comprehensive collection of datasets to predict aerodynamic sound emissions and propagation from wind turbines. It also uses New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) data to assess wind conditions relevant to noise propagation.

Concerning shadow flickers, we have developed a Python tool to assess its intensity (in hours per year) for individual turbines. It requires as input the location, time, and a simplified geometrical representation of the turbine. The results are close to the ones that can be obtained with the industry and academic standards. The data set includes examples of calculating one location in different temporal resolutions when performing the shadow flicker assessment. The developed tool can deliver a high-level shadow flicker assessment in seconds and is open source, which should ensure its integration into the WIMBY Web-GIS. Follow-up work towards D2.4. will include improving calculation speed and adding further parameters to the model.

Finally, a comprehensive risk assessment of onshore and offshore wind power accidents is developed based on the established framework for evaluating energy technologies. The focus is on occupational and public human health risks and calculating relevant risk indicators such as accident, fatality, and injury rates. For this purpose, a global accident database is compiled that builds upon publicly available data and covers events since 2000. Next, data are evaluated for

different attributes (e.g., accident types, etc.), temporal and geographic trends, and normalised risk indicators are calculated. Lastly, an accident risk tool is produced, providing spatially disaggregated risk indicators maps for Europe, which will also be integrated into the WIMBY Web-GIS.

The report outlines each tool's methodology, data acquisition, analysis, and development process, highlighting its potential to aid policymakers and planners in evaluating the impacts of wind turbine installations. The tools' implications for sustainable wind energy development are significant, offering a resource for balancing renewable energy goals with community well-being. Future enhancements and potential applications in other regions are also discussed.

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ABBREVIATIONS

Acronym	Description
COP	Conference of the Parties
dB	decibel
dB(A)	A-weighted decibel
ENSAD	ENergy-related Severe Accident Database
EPSG	European Petroleum Survey Group Geodesy
GIS	Geographic information system
GW	Gigawatt
GWeyr	Gigawatt-electric-year
kb	Kilobytes
LCA	Life-cycle Assessment
L_{den}	Noise level day-evening-night
Mb	Mega-bytes
NGO	Non-Governmental Organization
NLP	Natural Language Processing
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SaS	Scotland against Spin
SF	Shadow flicker
WHO	World Health Organisation

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report introduces the work on noise, shadow flicker and accident risk assessment.

Regarding noise impact assessment, we developed an innovative Python model designed to predict the noise emissions of wind turbines and their impact on the surrounding residential areas, aligning with the objectives of the WIMBY project. The model leverages advanced machine learning techniques to accurately estimate the Noise level day-evening-night (L_{den}) levels experienced by communities near wind turbines, emphasizing compliance with WHO noise guidelines. A key feature of this study is the creation of a comprehensive map illustrating wind turbines in Switzerland and the affected population, mainly focusing on areas where the L_{den} exceeds WHO recommended thresholds. The methodology adopted in this work represents a significant step towards understanding and mitigating the environmental impact of wind turbine noise, offering valuable insights for policymakers and industry stakeholders, developed entirely within an open-source framework.

While the model shows promising results, we also acknowledge the challenges faced, such as dependency on specific data sources such as NEWA, and the need for customisation across different geographic contexts before its final use in a European context.

Concerning shadow flicker, we have conducted a systematic literature review to determine the most used tools to assess it. We thoroughly analysed parameters, calculation speed, and accuracy of the industry and academic standard WindPRO to determine the minimum temporal and spatial resolutions to allow an accurate shadow flicker assessment. We also tested multiple open-source tools for shadow calculation that we expected to allow adaption for shadow flicker calculation. This proved unsuccessful, and we implemented an own tool in Python. This tool requires the location (wgs84 latitude and longitude) and a simplified representation of the turbine's geometry as input. Results are close to the ones that can be obtained with the industry standard for the worst-case scenario calculation (no consideration of, e.g., wind speeds and cloudiness) concerning calculation speed and calculated shadow flicker intensity in hours per year

for specific locations. Like the noise impact assessment tool, the shadow flicker tool is also open-source and lightweight, which should facilitate its integration into the WIMBY Web GIS. The provided data includes examples of calculating one location in different temporal resolutions when performing the shadow flicker assessment. These show the level of accuracy that could be obtained with the tool and the types of (files) of the possible outputs. While the current implementation of the tool is optimised and partially performed in multi-core, towards D2.4, we expect to improve the calculation time and include further parameters that would allow an assessment beyond the worst-case scenario calculation.

Concerning risk assessment of wind power accidents, a comprehensive methodological approach has been developed based on the state-of-the-art framework for comparative risk assessment implemented in the ENergy-related Severe Accident Database (ENSAD), the most authoritative global database for accidents in the energy sector. Furthermore, several modules and features have been added to achieve the specific risk assessment goals of the WIMBY project. This includes an open-access accident database based on publicly available information sources, calculation of spatially disaggregated risk indicators that provide the basis for high-resolution risk maps for Europe, and integration of the wind power accident mapping tool in the WIMBY Web-GIS.

1. Introduction and Background

1.1 Introduction to the Project

1.1.1 WIMBY overview and objectives

The WIMBY project represents a critical initiative in sustainable energy, focusing on integrating wind turbines in European landscapes. With the European Union's growing commitment to renewable energy, the need to balance technological advancement with environmental and social impacts is paramount.

1.1.2 Importance of wind energy in Europe

Europe has been at the forefront of embracing renewable energy sources, and wind energy plays a pivotal role in this transition. The continent's commitment to sustainability and reducing carbon emissions has positioned wind energy as a critical contributor to its energy mix. Europe currently has 255 GW of wind capacity and is expected to install an additional 90 GW in the next five years, reaching 277 GW of installed capacity by 2023¹. Countries like Germany, Spain, and the UK will continue to lead in wind energy capacity, with three-quarters of the new capacity additions expected to be onshore.

A significant investment of €208 billion is projected for new wind energy assets in Europe by 2023. This investment indicates a robust commitment to developing the renewable energy sector, with Germany, France, and Spain leading the wind energy installation growth in Europe over the next five years¹. More recently, the European Commission and 118 other countries have pledged to triple the installed capacity of renewable energy during the COP 28 meeting – although the exact share that will be attributed to wind power has not been elicited².

Despite its benefits, integrating wind turbines into European landscapes brings challenges, particularly concerning their noise emissions and their impact on local communities. This has led to a nuanced discourse on the balance between renewable energy expansion and environmental

stewardship. As discussed in this report, developing a transparent and open-source noise mapping tool is a response to these challenges.

Noise emissions are not the only potential issue. The rotating shadows created by wind turbines, known as 'shadow flicker' (SF), are unlikely to adversely affect the health of nearby populations, especially for mid to large-sized wind turbines³. While potential health impacts, particularly for individuals susceptible to photosensitive epilepsy, are expected if the flicker frequency exceeds 2.5 Hz., most wind turbines larger than 500 kW operate at speeds resulting in flicker frequencies below 1 Hz. Apart from health concerns, prolonged exposure to low-frequency SF has been linked to increased stress. Studies like the one by Paul et al.⁴ suggest that a one-time exposure to a 60-minute duration of SF can induce stress reactions. The occurrence of such events depends on factors like distance, local topography, sun altitude, wind direction, and cloudiness, necessitating a detailed local analysis to understand the potential SF-related annoyance for the local population. Some cases indicate limited to no exposure for individuals living just a few hundred meters from wind turbines^{3,5}. Numerous studies suggest that only a small fraction of the population finds SF annoying.^{6,7} A comprehensive survey for the United States of America by Haac et al.⁵ reveals that self-reported annoyance is not linked to the modelled SF exposure level but is influenced by subjective factors such as project appearance and general annoyance. Levels of modelled SF exposure correlate with self-reported annoyance, and easy-to-implement technical solutions, like planned curtailment, are available³.

In contrast to noise and shadow flicker, health impacts due to accidents are often restricted to an occupational risk perspective, whereas risks to the population near a wind farm and societal risks in general receive significantly less attention⁸⁻¹¹. Quantitative risk assessment is based on mathematical modelling methods, making it difficult to understand for non-experts and the public. Risks of energy technologies represent systemic risks because they are embedded in a multi-faceted and complex system with many elements and processes that need to be considered in failure analysis and the resulting consequences¹². Furthermore, expected (objective) risks can be challenged by public perception, and recent experience demonstrates how disinformation campaigns can intensify support for

conspiracy beliefs¹³, which ultimately can lead to strong opposition and, in some cases, violent protests^{14,15}. In particular, there is a notable gap in the analysis and discussion of objective and quantifiable risks and their associated consequences concerning wind turbine accidents. This gap is mainly due to inadequate accident reporting, limited public availability of incident data, and a general lack of verified and structured data¹⁶.

1.2 Problem Statement

1.2.1 Wind turbine noise impacts on nearby buildings

Wind turbines, while beneficial for clean energy production, pose a challenge regarding noise emissions, show flickers, and raise safety concerns.

Concerning noise emissions, these emissions can significantly affect marine^{17,18} and terrestrial^{19–21} ecosystems and the quality of life of individuals living near wind farms^{22,23}. Adherence to the World Health Organisation's noise guidelines is essential for minimizing these impacts²⁴.

The World Health Organisation (WHO) has established comprehensive guidelines on environmental noise, aiming to protect public health. These guidelines are crucial as they provide evidence-based recommendations on maximum noise levels to prevent adverse health effects in populations exposed to various noise sources, including wind turbines¹⁰. For wind turbine installations, adhering to WHO noise guidelines is particularly important. These guidelines ensure that the noise levels produced by wind turbines do not exceed levels that could lead to health issues such as sleep disturbance, cardiovascular diseases, or hearing impairment in nearby residential areas.

The WHO guidelines benchmark acceptable noise exposure, guiding policymakers and developers in planning and executing wind energy projects. Compliance with these guidelines is critical to maintaining public support for wind energy projects, as it demonstrates a commitment to minimizing the environmental and social impacts of renewable energy expansion.

1.2.2 Wind turbine shadow flickers impacts

Concerning shadow flickers, the primary challenge addressed in this project is to accurately assess and understand the exposure of populations to them caused by wind turbines, particularly those larger than 500 KW. While existing studies suggest that SF is unlikely to have significant health impacts, especially for mid to large-sized turbines, there is evidence linking prolonged exposure to low-frequency SF with increased stress levels. The variability in individual reactions to SF, influenced by distance from turbines, local topography, the Sun's altitude, wind direction, and cloudiness, necessitates a detailed analysis to gauge potential annoyance among local populations. Additionally, self-reported annoyance is influenced by subjective factors beyond mere exposure levels.

1.2.3 Risk assessment of wind turbines

Finally, the lack of a comprehensive accident risk assessment framework and publicly available facts and knowledge challenges wind farm developers, government authorities, and regulators, ultimately preventing them from making informed decisions. Furthermore, it can lead to incomplete and biased understanding by diverse, affected stakeholders (e.g., NGOs, sectoral associations, etc.) and the public, which hampers the implementation of facts-based, participatory processes to discuss and resolve potential subjective concerns and perceptions and to achieve widely acceptable solutions. This underpins the need for a transparent, consistent, and robust risk assessment framework that allows quantifying diverse safety and health impact metrics to evaluate project and site-specific risks, generic risks at larger geographic scales, and to compare wind power with other electricity generation technologies²⁵.

1.3 Aims of the Tools

1.3.1 Purpose of the noise impact mapping tool

This tool aims to map the noise emissions of existing and hypothetical wind turbines across Europe, identifying populations affected by noise, specifically those exceeding WHO-recommended L_{den} thresholds. This tool

facilitates informed decision-making in wind energy development and community planning.

Although very simple in its current state, the tool may provide valuable insights for policymakers, planners, and citizens once finalised. Coupled with the over-arching Web-GIS tool developed within WIMBY under WP5, it will facilitate informed decision-making by highlighting the potential noise impact of existing wind turbine installations, enabling the selection of optimal locations for new turbines, and implementing noise mitigation strategies.

Currently, the tool can:

- Predict noise emissions at the turbine location as a function of power, hub diameter, and height for various wind speed levels,
- Calculate noise emissions over a period, based on wind speed time series of a specific location,
- Calculate cumulative emissions of near-located wind turbines (i.e., wind farms),
- Calculate the exposure to noise of listening points (e.g., nearby residents) in dB(A) and its perceived impact using the L_{den} metric.

In the remaining project development, the following capabilities should be added:

- Account for wind direction, topography, and obstacles in noise propagation,
- Derive other human health-related metrics, such as Disability-adjusted life-years, if possible normalised by electricity production (e.g., DALY/kWh)^{26,27},
- Derive metrics for terrestrial ecosystems,
- Integrate into the life-cycle assessment library *windisch*¹, also developed within the WIMBY project.

1.3.2 Purpose of the shadow flicker impact mapping tool

¹ <https://github.com/romainsacchi/windisch>

The tool aims to assess the exposure of populations to shadow flickers from individual wind parks. Discarding health issues, the focus is on the physical exposure of populations to SF and its potential correlation with stakeholder annoyance. This tool is intended for integration into WIMBY's WEB-GIS, requiring high accuracy, fast computation times, and open-source compatibility.

1.3.3 Purpose of the risk mapping tool

The overarching goal of the risk assessment of wind power accidents carried out in the WIMBY project is to provide comparative and quantitative results, taking a societal perspective. To do so, a consistent and comprehensive data set of wind power accidents is compiled, which builds exclusively upon publicly available information. First, an explorative analysis is carried out to describe time and geographic trends and patterns for selected attributes (e.g., types of accidents). Second, selected indicators (e.g., numbers of accidents, fatalities, injuries) are calculated for different country groups and on-/offshore activities. Compare for a detailed description and preliminary results ²⁸. Third, a geospatial wind farm accident tool is developed that can be incorporated into the WIMBY Web-GIS.

This deliverable presents a preliminary version of the tool, which aims to visually represent wind turbine accidents as an interactive map. It allows the user to explore locations of wind turbine accidents since 2000 and gain detailed information on the spatial distribution, characteristics and consequences of the accidents.

Currently, the tool provides the following basic features:

- Display of an interactive map of wind farm accidents
- Provision of specific information for each accident (i.e., pop-up), including date and type of incident, human health impacts (i.e., fatalities and injuries), and associated wind farm details.
- Enhanced visual interpretation through colour-coded markers based on the severity of accidents (fatalities, injuries, no consequences).

The accident risk mapping tool will be further developed for this deliverable's final version, and new features will be added.

- Time-based filtering: allows filtering and visualizing accidents based on specific periods and date ranges.

- Other filter options to display accident sub-sets according to specific characteristics and attributes.
- Provide aggregated (i.e., normalised) risk indicators for numbers of accidents, fatalities, and injuries at high spatial resolution.
- Secondary information layers: incorporate additional map layers with information on wind turbines and wind farms (e.g., characteristics, density, and distribution, etc.), regional statistics, and environmental factors (e.g., wind speed, power density, etc.).

2. Noise Impact Assessment

2.1 Methodology Overview

2.1.1 Basics of Sound and Noise Measurement

Sound measurement is essential in assessing the environmental impact of noise. It involves quantifying the intensity of sound as perceived by the human ear using a logarithmic scale known as the decibel (dB) scale. This measurement helps to establish baselines, assess compliance with noise standards, and develop noise mitigation strategies.

2.1.1.1 Decibel scale and A-weighted sound levels

The decibel (dB) scale is a logarithmic unit used to express sound intensity. A-weighted sound levels (dBA) adjust the raw decibel measurements to reflect the varying sensitivity of the human ear to different frequencies, giving more weight to frequencies that are more audible to humans. This is crucial for accurately evaluating potential noise disturbances from wind turbines.

2.1.2 Noise emissions from wind turbines

Wind turbines produce noise emissions that can impact nearby residents. These emissions are categorised into *mechanical* and *aerodynamic* sources, each with distinct characteristics and implications for noise management. Understanding these emissions is vital for predicting their impact and implementing appropriate mitigation measures.

2.1.2.1 Mechanical and aerodynamic noise sources

Mechanical noise in wind turbines originates from moving components such as gearboxes and generators. Aerodynamic noise is caused by air interaction with the turbine blades. While engineering advancements have minimised mechanical noises, aerodynamic noise remains a significant source, influencing the overall sound profile of wind turbines.

2.1.2.2 Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Regression and data sources

Estimating aerodynamic noise computationally is complex. Instead, we rely on noise measurements conducted on 227 wind turbines, encompassing 1'550 distinct noise emission levels provided by WindPRO². Histogram-based Gradient Boosting Regression, an advanced Machine Learning algorithm, was employed to develop the tool for predicting noise emissions from wind turbines. This method builds upon an ensemble of decision trees, leveraging their collective insights to make predictions based on input factors. The model underwent training using data from the above source to obtain excellent levels of prediction accuracy for the various wind speed levels.

Hence, for a given location, power, and hub height and diameter, the tool predicts noise levels function of wind speed, as shown in Figure 1 for a selection of installations.

² <https://www.emd-international.com/windpro/>

Figure 1 A-weighted noise levels [dBA] as a function of wind speed [m/s] for five distinct wind turbines. The data represent user-inputted specifications for each of the five turbines.

2.1.2.3 Aerodynamic noise propagation

Estimating noise propagation is a complex task that requires the consideration of various environmental factors. These include the geometric spread of sound waves, their atmospheric absorption, and the effects of terrain and obstructions. Additionally, wind speed and direction are pivotal in noise propagation from the source. Noise propagation is, therefore, often obtained using calculation-intensive simulations (see [pywake³](#), [WindPRO⁴](#)).

Our simplified noise propagation model focuses on the two most influential factors: the geometric spreading of sound and atmospheric sound absorption, which strongly depend on the distance between the wind turbine and the listening point.

Future work is anticipated to incorporate other influential elements, notably the topographical and obstruction-induced effects on noise distribution, which are particularly relevant in the presence of local structures like

³ <https://github.com/DTUWindEnergy/PyWake>

⁴ <https://www.emd-international.com/windpro/>

buildings or wooded areas. The challenge is mostly regarding getting this information for any location in Europe.

Given the location of wind turbines and listening points (i.e., exposed to noise), our model can estimate the noise level the listeners are exposed to, as shown in Figure 2, solely based on the geometric spreading of sound and atmospheric sound absorption.

Figure 2 Noise propagation at a wind speed of 7 m/s for five wind turbines and noise exposure level for three listening points.

The reader should note that the tool does consider the wind speed and direction on noise propagation, as it turns out to have a negligible effect at high altitudes (> 5m), according to WindPRO simulations.

2.2 Data Acquisition and Analysis

Acquiring and analysing accurate data is crucial for assessing wind turbine noise and its impact on the surrounding population. This involves collecting wind and noise level data and understanding how these levels change throughout the day and night, which is where L_{den} measurement comes into play.

2.2.1 Wind data and L_{den} measurement

Accurate wind data is essential for forecasting the noise emissions from wind turbines since there is a direct correlation between the noise intensity and the wind speed. Furthermore, the periods during which wind turbines generate noise significantly influence the disturbance experienced by nearby residents.

For that purpose, the tool relies on historical wind data, utilizing a 30-minute interval time series provided by the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA)⁵ for specific European locations.

The Day-Evening-Night Level (L_{den}) is a critical metric used in noise assessment, representing a 24-hour average sound level with added penalties of 5 and 10 dB(A) for evening and night periods, respectively, to account for higher human sensitivity to noise during these periods. The formula used to calculate the L_{den} of one or several wind turbines at a specific location is:

$$L_{den} = 10 * \log_{10} \left(\frac{1}{24} (12L_d + 4(5 + L_e) + 8(10 + L_n)) \right)$$

with L_d , L_e , and L_n being the average noise level the listening points are exposed to during the day, evening, and night periods, respectively.

Provided a wind speed time series averaged over a certain period, mean wind speed values per hour of the day are obtained. They are used to calculate the L_{den} , considering the distribution of the noise exposure over the day. The recommended L_{den} limit set by the WHO for wind turbines is 45 dBa.

2.3 Tool Development and Mapping Process

⁵ <https://map.neweuropeanwindatlas.eu/>

The tool is developed under a permissive BSD 3-Clause license. It uses the programming language Python, and its code is entirely hosted and documented on GitHub⁶.

The tool's workflow is the following:

1. Input a list of wind turbines defined by their power output, hub height, diameter, and geographic coordinates.
2. Fetch historical wind speed data series for each turbine's location using the New European Wind Atlas (NEWA) API. Transform each wind speed into noise emission over time (two years by default).
3. Use the ML Histogram-based Gradient Boosting model to predict noise levels based on downloaded wind speed and turbine characteristics.
4. Simulate noise propagation from wind turbines to assess the noise the surrounding populations perceive.

Additionally, for the case study presented here, the following steps are followed:

5. Locate residence buildings in Switzerland.
6. Identify buildings within the perceptible noise range of one or several wind turbines.
7. Calculate the L_{den} for each building within the noise propagation area of one or several wind turbines.

Data on the location of residence buildings in Switzerland is obtained from the Swiss Federal Office of Statistics, identifying 3,214,737 buildings⁷. The location of the 50 wind turbines (including the specifications required by the tool, such as power, hub height, and diameter) in Switzerland is obtained from the Swiss Federal Office of Energy via opendata.swiss⁸.

⁶ <https://github.com/Maxbeal/noisemodel>

⁷ <https://www.housing-stat.ch/fr/madd/public.html>

⁸ <https://opendata.swiss/de/dataset/windenergieanlagen> last time visited on 12/2023

2.4 Mapping Noise Impacts of Wind Turbines in Switzerland

The file *Lden_map_Switzerland_2023-12-04.html*, provided together with this document, shows the results of the analysis of the noise impact of the 50 wind turbines located in Switzerland. The maps find wind turbine installations and residence buildings within the noise propagation area of the wind turbines. We colour-coded the icons for residences exposed to an average noise level superior to the L_{den} value recommended by the WHO in red and dark red (see Figure 3).

The reader should note that the current stage of development of the tool (notably the lack of consideration of complex topographies and the presence of obstacles), as well as the lack of model validation, does not allow us to confirm whether the noise and related annoyance, are indeed perceived with the intensity indicated on the map.

Figure 3 Location of wind turbines and residence buildings exposed to noise near La Chaux-de-Fonds, Neuchâtel, Switzerland. Residence buildings not within the noise-perceptible range are not shown on the map.

2.5 Conclusions

The open-source noise impact model developed in the first year of the WIMBY project presents a sophisticated approach to predicting noise emissions from wind turbines, offering several advantages but also facing some challenges. Notably, the model's integration of machine learning algorithms and wind data provides a robust platform for accurate noise emission predictions and a valuable visualisation feature for stakeholders to assess the impact on surrounding areas. However, the complexity of modelling atmospheric sound absorption and the reliance on high-quality, comprehensive data sets pose potential limitations to the tool's effectiveness. Additionally, the model's application across different European regions may require adjustments to address varying geographical and climatic conditions and obtain data on populations for these regions. This balance of strengths and challenges highlights the tool's potential in assessing wind turbine noise emissions while underlining areas for further development and refinement.

2.5.1 Future Work and Enhancement

The noise impact assessment tool will be improved concerning the following aspects.

- Better consideration of environmental factors in the noise propagation model (precisely the effect of wind speed and direction, topography, and obstacles),
- Validation of the noise propagation model (possibly via on-site noise level measurements)
- Inclusion of additional metrics to represent noise-related impacts on humans and nearby ecosystems.
- Data acquisition on residential infrastructure for the rest of Europe.
- Integration with the life-cycle assessment tool developed within Task 2.4.

3. Shadow flicker impact assessment

3.1 Systematic literature review on shadow flicker assessment

3.1.1 Data Sources and Search

Through a systematic literature review, we aim to comprehensively summarize the current knowledge of wind turbine SF and its assessment. We focus on the (potential) impacts of SF, the tools used to assess it and which parameter plays a role. By performing a general Google search on SF, we came across extensive reports on shadow flickers, such as the one of Parsons Brinckerhoff ³ for the UK Department of Energy and Climate Change or Pohl et al. ⁴ for the Ministry of Environment of Lower Saxony and Bavaria in Germany. These reports are somewhat dated but contribute to policymaking in these countries. These also already show that SF is a source of annoyance for the nearby population and discard health issues related to larger turbines. Turbines were considerably smaller in 1999²⁹, and their rotation frequency would not reach values that would affect even the part of the population most prone to have health issues derived from SF (individuals susceptible to photosensitive epilepsy). We, therefore, discard health issues related to SF coming from larger turbines with even lower rotation frequencies. Based on these readings and willing to understand how we can identify the parts of the population that could be potentially annoyed by SF, we run the following search in SCOPUS:

```
TITLE-ABS-KEY ( ("wind" ) AND ( "shadow" OR "shadow flicker" ) AND ( "health" OR "risk" OR "annoyance" ) )
```

The search was conducted on June 7th, 2023, and the search result included 75 peer-reviewed journal articles. We reviewed titles and abstracts in all languages, but in the end, non-English literature was not fit for the analysis due to the less relevant content (see exclusion criteria).

3.1.2 Exclusion criteria and final set of articles to review

We first used the AI-supported software *Rayyan* ³⁰ to screen through the articles, deciding to include or exclude studies based on keyword content

and whether the study abstract was relevant to the impacts on wind power infrastructure. We excluded articles that were out of scope, articles that focused on the technical details of wind turbines, articles about solely the operation of wind parks, or articles that focused on the impacts of offshore wind farms (we do not expect expressed annoyance from SF produced by offshore installations). After this round of scanning, 53 papers were excluded, leaving only 22 papers (Figure 4).

Next, we went through a full-article text assessment by reading the whole article, excluding the four papers focusing on something other than shadow flicker or other health-related impacts of wind energy. While assessing full articles, we explored more relevant studies in the article references (snowball principle). Therefore, we included six more papers in this process.

Figure 4. Decision-making tree of systematic literature review on shadow flicker assessment.

3.1.3 Literature review coding (Classification)

In the full-text assessment, we coded the included papers based on the criteria in

Table 1. Through this process, we were able to conclude the primary methodologies used for shadow flicker impact assessment and compare the methods, tools, and databases included in different pieces of literature. In total, 24 papers were coded according to these criteria.

Table 1 Criteria for literature review coding on shadow flicker impacts assessment.

Literature review criteria	Definitions
Authors	Author names of the paper
Title	Title of the paper
Year	Publication year
Methodology	The main methodology for flicker impact assessment
Methodology of shadow flicker calculation	Methodology specifically for shadow flicker (physical) calculation, if existed
Database	The database being used in the research
Methodology details	Technical details of the methodology
Results	Main results of the paper (may include other health impacts or annoyance assessment)
Shadow flicker	Results relevant to shadow flicker impacts assessment
Group number	The group number of the sample if a statistical method or empirical research was applied
Location (city, country/ region)	The spatial scope of the research
Modelling software or tool	If a modelling method was applied, which software or tool was being used
Modelling parameters	If a modelling method was applied, what were the critical parameters included in the modelling work
General annoyance notes	Other notes for general annoyance assessment
Modelling note	Additional notes for modelling details or boundaries

3.1.4 Study assessment results

The distribution of assessment methods and approaches for SF impacts is summarised in **Table 2**. Some research included more than one assessment method, counted as different methods.

Since the goal is to develop an assessment tool for SF that can be integrated into the WIMBY Web-GIS, we focused on the research that included modelling methodologies and checked the models or tools they used. As a result, three out of five papers used windPRO as (part of) the assessment tool; the other two papers were, in the end, not focused on shadow flicker impacts specifically. Therefore, we can conclude that 1) most research on SF does not take into consideration the actual physical area that might be affected by SF and that 2) windPRO is not only an industry standard to conduct this analysis, but it is also the dominant and default model in academic research.

Table 2. Methodology summary of the literature on shadow flicker impacts assessment.

Methodology	Counts
Literature review	7
Empirical research	7
Epidemiological study	5
Modelling and mathematical calculation	7
LCA (life cycle assessment)	1
SIA (social impact assessment)	1
Environmental impact assessment	1
Visibility assessment	1
Medical database analysis	1

Furthermore, the fundamental parameters affecting SF, derived from our literature review, span a range of factors from turbine characteristics to environment and terrain. These parameters are summarised in [Table 3](#) and explained in the following paragraphs (based on findings from Haac R. et al.⁵ and S. Voicescu et al.³¹).

- **Turbine:** This category includes various data points specific to the wind turbine and the project. Critical aspects are the hub height of the turbine, its rotor diameter, blade width, and the geographical location of the turbine.
- **Sun:** The Sun's position plays a pivotal role in the dynamics of shadow flicker. It determines the angle and length of the shadows cast by the turbine.
- **Meteorology:** Meteorological conditions are also crucial. This encompasses the wind direction and speed, which can affect the orientation and operation of the turbine, and cloud cover, which can mitigate or exacerbate shadow flicker.
- **Topography:** The topography and land cover surrounding the turbine influence shadow flicker. The contours of the land and the presence of various land covers can alter the extent and intensity of shadows.

These parameters collectively contribute to understanding SF phenomena and are essential for developing accurate predictive models.

Table 3. Summary of the critical parameters that affect shadow flicker from literature review ^{5,31}

The key parameters that affect shadow flicker			
Turbine (Wind turbine and project data)	Sun	Meteorology	Topography
the hub height of the turbine	the position of the Sun	wind direction	topography and land cover
its rotor diameter and blade width		wind speed	
location		cloud cover	

3.2 Testing the Industry and academic standard: windPRO

Before model development, we tested critical parameters in windPRO since windPRO is what we found to be the SF calculation standard in industry and academia. We conducted dozens of tests to understand the trade-offs between accuracy and computational time. windPRO’s SF calculator cannot be integrated directly into the Web-GIS because of its computational overhead and commercial character (i.e., not an open-source software). By evaluating windPRO's parameters, we aim to define which are essential to obtain a swift calculation that keeps most of the accuracy of the calculation.

3.2.1 WindPRO test parameters

There are some parameters that we assumed would influence the accuracy and the calculation time of shadow flickers. The main ones that are adjustable in windPRO 3.6 include the calculated area (rectangle from the centre of the turbine), the resolution (coarse, regular, fine), use of obstacles (with porosity < 0.4) or not, use of topographic shadow or not, and change of the observer’s eyes height.

During the testing phase, we selected the Siemens Gamesa SG 5.0-132 turbine as our model for simulation, methodically altering one variable at a time to monitor the effects. Our objective with the calculated area was to determine the minimal geographical extent necessary to represent shadow flicker impact across Europe accurately. Concerning resolution, our goal was to juxtapose the outcomes of varying degrees of resolution to

understand the minimum resolution (in time and space) we should aim for while keeping most of the accuracy and minimizing the calculation time.

Concerning obstacles, observer's eye height, and topographic shadow, our exploration was centred on understanding their respective contributions to the shadow flicker calculations. We sought to quantify how these elements influence the results' accuracy and the computational process's efficiency. This thorough examination aims to identify potential optimisations in modelling shadow flicker effects.

3.2.2 *WindPRO test results*

Upon conducting a series of sensitivity tests by changing the variables above for the fixed locations to investigate their influences on calculation results, we discerned that including obstacles and alterations to the observer's eye height exert a negligible effect on the computational duration and the outcome. Given these findings, we have resolved to exclude these factors from our shadow flicker model. Furthermore, our experiments revealed that incorporating topographic shadows could potentially increase the calculation time by a factor of forty, even at the coarsest resolution. Given this substantial increase, we have decided to omit topographic shadows from our calculations in D2.3 and will evaluate alternatives for inclusion in 2.4.

Our focus then shifted to the most critical parameters for high-level but accurate estimation of the SF extent and intensity: the dimensions of the calculated area and the resolution settings. Testing was undertaken to evaluate the sensitivity and output variance related to these parameters. Specifically, for the estimated area, we examined distances of 2, 3, 5, and 10 kilometres from the centre of the site across three distinct European locations—namely the Netherlands, France, and Norway. The results indicated that a 3-kilometre radius from the site centre generally encapsulates the region affected by shadow flicker in these test cases (see [Table 4](#)). Consequently, our model has adopted this dimension as the standard calculation area for shadow flicker impacts.

Table 4. WindPRO tests for different calculated rectangles from the site centre (km).

Flicker map for one turbine (Siemens Gamesa SG 5.0-132 MkII 5000 132.0 !O!)							
Resolution: coarse							
Worst case scenario (not accounting for, e.g., cloudiness and wind speeds, which would reduce the SF)							
Calculated rectangle from the site centre (km)				NL case	FR case	NO case	
E	W	S	N	calculation time (seconds)		Note	
2	2	2	2	4	7	4	It cannot cover the whole shadow flicker impact region
3	3	3	3	5	8	5	Can cover the entire shadow flicker impact region
5	5	5	5	7	12	6	Can cover the entire shadow flicker impact region
10	10	10	10	14	22	10	Can cover the entire shadow flicker impact region

For the three distinct resolution settings available in windPRO, we documented the computational time and analysed the resultant shadow coverage areas, which are reported in the following tables. The tests were run using a business laptop with AMD Ryzen 7 4700U with Radeon Graphics 2.00 GHz, eight cores, and 16 GB of RAM. This evaluation was essential to ascertain the trade-offs between the results' precision and the calculation process's efficiency. Our analysis led us to an insightful conclusion: the shadow coverage area computed at the coarse resolution setting ranges from 93% to 97.95% when juxtaposed with the outcomes derived from the fine resolution. Based on this comparative study, we assert that the coarse resolution setting suffices for our modelling approach (maximum 7% accuracy loss, mainly for areas where the SF intensity is lower than four hours per year). The pertinent data supporting this conclusion is presented in [Table 5](#) and [Table 6](#). An example of the results of the calculation made with WindPRO is provided in Figure 5 (the legend of that figure reflects the meaning of the column "Shadow hours" in [Table 6](#))

Table 5. WindPRO tests for different resolutions and the resolution definitions.

Worst-case statistics, case NL			
3 km from the site centre rectangle is calculated			
8,000 operational hours			
Resolution	Calculation time (seconds)	File Size (MB)	Resolution definition
Coarse	7	0.1	Time step: 4 minutes, Day step: 14 days, Map resolution: 30 m
Normal	28	0.1	Time step: 3 minutes, Day step: 7 days, Map resolution: 20 m
Fine	430	0.3	Time step: 2 minutes, Day step: 3 days, Map resolution: 10 m

Table 6. WindPRO tests results for different resolutions and the cover area comparisons.

Shadow hours	Shadow cover area (m²)			Shadow cover area comparison		
	Coarse	Normal	Fine	Coarse	Normal	Fine
30	355,795	362,003	363,225	97.95%	99.66%	100.00%
8	1,218,668	1,228,380	1,235,386	98.65%	99.43%	100.00%
4	2,053,826	2,071,331	2,086,514	98.43%	99.27%	100.00%
0.015	9,078,586	9,286,535	9,761,231	93.01%	95.14%	100.00%

Map: EMD OpenStreetMap , Print scale 1:40,000, Map center Geo WGS84 East: 5.576083° E North: 53.126012° N

Figure 5 Results example from WindPRO. Time step: 4 minutes, Day step: 14 days, Map resolution: 30 m for our test location in the Netherlands.

3.3 Shadow flicker model in Python

3.3.1 Existing shadow (flicker) programming code

In the initial stages of constructing our shadow flicker model, our approach included an exhaustive search for pre-existing open-source software that could either directly calculate SF or be used as a basis for such calculation. Consistently with the results of our review, where the standard is the use of WindPRO, we could not find a tool that would directly make the SF calculation. We evaluated and tested several packages with shadow calculations to understand their functionalities and determine their applicability to our project's requirements. We excluded libraries implemented in full GIS environments, such as QGIS and GRASSGIS, to avoid the computational overhead of having to run and keep the file structure of these tools in the background. We read full descriptions and related scientific publications and inspected the code of tools such as *pybdshadow* 0.3.4⁹, *pyny3d*¹⁰, *Shadowtime*¹¹, and the R library *shadow*³². We discarded tools for which development was no longer supported, tools requiring a complete 3D environment, and tools whose output could only be transformed/understood as SF with difficulty. From the previous list, the only tool showing some potential was the shadow package in R (subsequently called shadow-R), which was developed initially to analyse the shadow cast by buildings in the urban environment.

3.3.2 Assumptions and inputs and description of the SF calculator

We decided to thoroughly assess the shadow-R package and compare results to a tool implemented from scratch in Python, subsequently called the WIMBY-SF calculator. We employed a vertical rectangular column for the shadow-R tests to symbolize the wind turbine. This would be as high as the turbine's total height (i.e., the sum of hub height and radius of the blades), and the length is equivalent to the diameter of the turbine. The width was set to 20m (this should be enough to represent the cumulated width of the tower and blades of most wind turbines). For the WIMBY-SF calculator, we

⁹ <https://pypi.org/project/pybdshadow/>

¹⁰ https://pythonhosted.org/pyny3d/tutorial_basic_shadowing.html

¹¹ <https://github.com/davidosterberg/shadowtime>

assumed an object footprint that is a circle around the turbine coordinates and has the same radius as the actual turbines. This could be understood as a cylinder with an altitude equal to the sum of the hub height and the radius of the blades. This difference between the representation of a turbine seems appropriate since shadow-R calculates the full shadow length of the object (from the bottom to the top, which would include not only the blades of the turbine but also the tower). At the same time, for the WIMBY-SF calculator, we can directly estimate the expected footprint of the spinning blades in a 2D approximation.

For comparability with the “worst case” results of WindPRO (largest possible extent and frequency of SF), we assume ideal clear-sky conditions, thereby omitting cloud cover and meteorological data from our initial calculations. Furthermore, we initially disregarded the influence of topography on shadow projections.

The calculation details for the shadow footprint of shadow-R can be found in Dorman et al.³² For the WIMBY-SF calculator, we followed the same steps. We calculate the shadow length and direction based on the same formulas that depend on the Sun’s position (declination and elevation) at a particular moment, but we use the *solpos* library from NREL³³ and call it from the solar position wrapper *PVlib*³⁴. The implementation includes four functions: 1) to create the initial footprint, 2) to calculate the shadow footprint for one particular moment in time, excluding periods when the solar altitude is negative or when the shadow length goes beyond the size of the optimal assessment area (see [Table 4](#)), 3) to iterate in particular moments in a range of time. This delivers a geojson file with all shadow footprints for those specific moments, and 4) creates a raster map with the frequency of exposure to SF in hours. We also created single-core and multicore implementations (for the function that iterates in specific moments in time).

We tested the tools using the same turbine type and location in the Netherlands used for the tests of windPRO (i.e., a turbine with a hub height of 84 meters and diameter of 132 meters located at coordinates 5.588264, 53.123084). We assessed the required computational time and the accuracy.

3.3.3 Results

The WIMBY-SF calculator outperforms shadow-R for our purposes (shadow-R also has multiple extra features that are neither covered nor necessary in the WIMBY-SF calculator) and can be faster than WindPro in the fine calculation resolution (see [Table 7](#)). However, the calculation time of the normal and coarse resolution are longer, showing that there is still room for improvement concerning the computational requirements of the tool. The time taken and output file size of our implementations are presented in [Table 7](#). This includes the time necessary to create the polygon describing the turbine, the calculation of individual footprints and the aggregation of these footprints to obtain the SF frequency.

Table 7 Result table for model runs

Model	Resolution			Time taken (seconds)	File size (kb)	
	days	minutes	map		geojson	geoTIFF
Python single core	3	2	10	591.92	146,976	1,697
Python single core	7	3	20	152.57	41,868	416
Python single core	14	4	30	57.04	15,769	170
Python multi-core	3	2	10	258.64	146,976	1,697
Python multi-core	7	3	20	46.62	41,868	416
Python multi-core	14	4	30	17.52	15,769	170
shadow-R	3	2	10	565.88	9,187	3,060
shadow-R	7	3	20	229.12	3,927	282
shadow-R	14	4	30	60.56	1,957	267

Examples of individual shadow/SF footprints calculated with shadow-R and the WIMBY-SF calculator are presented in Figure 6. The main difference between both maps is that map a) only provides the final part of the shadow where the footprint of the turbine is expected while b) also includes the

shadow of the tower, which would modify the final SF density. The second main difference is the total coverage of the footprints. While a) the WIMBY-SF implementation overlaps over 95% of the WindPRO results (such as the ones in Figure 5), additional tuning would be necessary for b) shadow-R to reach the same coverage.

Figure 6. Vector representation of individual time steps for a) shadow flicker footprint using WIMBY-SF calculator and b) shadow footprint using shadow-R. Both for a temporal repetition of 3 days and 2 minutes.

Figure 7. Raster representation of the SF intensity in h/year for the a) fine, b) normal and c) coarse resolutions. All are calculated with the WIMBY-SF calculator.

The main difference between the individual resolutions is the area most distant to the turbine in the west and the east (see Figure 7). Most of these areas only have some minutes of SF exposition per year. The figure provided by WindPro (a vector probably derived from the contour of the raster maps like the ones we supply) clarifies which areas SF could affect. However, the division into only a few categories might invite us to believe that some areas have a considerably higher SF intensity than they have (e.g., the yellow area in Figure 5 with a range between 30 and 500 hours per year). Our current representation shows in a very high spatial resolution (10–30m depending on the setting), which are the surrounding areas of a turbine that have the highest intensity of SF (yellow areas in maps a), b) and c) in Figure 7). Through the WEB-GIS development process and the interaction with stakeholders, we will define, in the following months, which is the most convenient way to present the data.

3.4 Shadow flicker dataset

The provided data sets are the raster files with SF intensity presented in Figure 7 and the corresponding vector maps with the individual SF footprints as provided in a) of Figure 6 but for the three assessed resolutions. All are calculated with the WIMBY-SF calculator. The raster files are 'geotiff' files, with resolutions ranging from 10 to 30 meters and a non-data value of -32768. The vector maps are provided in 'geojson' format and include the

attributes “time” and “SF”. Time is recorded in the format DD-MM-YYYY hh:mm:ss, and “SF” is the shadow flicker intensity, which is equal for every single footprint and is calculated based on the temporal resolution of the iterations. All maps are provided in a European Petroleum Survey Group Geodesy (EPSG) code 3857, which has metric units and is widely used for tools with global coverage. All data sets have the same bounding box in that EPSG. A different EPSG will be evaluated during the integration process in the WIMBY Web-GIS. A summary of the data set and main characteristics is provided in **Table 8**. The datasets and all the metadata will be published in YODA.

Table 8. Summary of the provided data sets

Data set name	Type	Format	Spatial resolution/objects
SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_10_3_1_2	raster	geoTIFF	10X10m
SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_20_7_1_3	raster	geoTIFF	20X20m
SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_30_14_1_4	raster	geoTIFF	30X30m
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_10_3_1_2	vector	geojson	42,141
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_20_7_1_3	vector	geojson	12,001
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_30_14_1_4	vector	geojson	4,501

3.5 Future work

In the forthcoming months we aim to improve the calculation time and add critical parameters to the equation, such as cloudiness and wind speed.

For instance, only one part of the calculation, the iteration through time steps to calculate individual footprints, is now parallelised. We will evaluate if a multicore/multithread implementation would make sense in other parts of the code. We also use a wrapper for the *solpos* algorithm, and we will assess if there would be performance improvements by replacing the way we call the algorithm. We will also run the WIMBY-SF tool on one of UU’s servers to see the possible performance when it integrates with the WIMBY GIS web map. Next, we want to include the meteorology factors in the WIMBY-SF tool, including wind speed, wind direction, and cloud coverage. The first two will change the SF pattern (fewer time steps will have an SF footprint) and frequency. We expect to use typical distributions for these

parameters, and for this, we will rely on data provided in WIMBY task 1.1. and the corresponding Deliverable 1.1 Wind resources API (a).

The plan is to also to consider additional factors that influencing SF in the model, test their impact and the model performance with and without their contribution. These factors include topography effects on shadow flicker projection and topographic shadow. In the windPRO test in section 3, we have seen that including topographic shadow would increase the computation time significantly (from a few seconds to minutes). It is worth investigating to what extent we should include or exclude these factors to provide an open-source tool with fast computation and efficiently representative results. The key to our developments beyond accuracy is that the assessment of SF intensity can be appropriately communicated to stakeholders. Therefore, time will also be invested in finding optimal ways of presenting/aggregating our data.

3.6 Conclusion

Through a systematic literature review on shadow flicker impact and testing different existing open-source tools, we acknowledge that WindPRO is the industry and academic standard tool to model its physical impact, with easily adjustable input variables and validate results. To fulfil the need of the WIMBY project, where we need an open-source tool that produces the GIS data that can integrate with the WIMBY GIS interactive map easily, with sufficient results but short computation time, we decided to develop our own Python-based shadow flicker calculator.

By testing the modelling performance and results, we conclude that the WIMBY-SF tool we developed outperformed shadow-R, based on existing open-source code, for our purposes. Compared to WindPRO in our modelling case, WIMBY-SF can be faster using a fine resolution. At the same time, WinPRO surpasses our current computing time for normal and coarse resolutions – but in a similar time magnitude. Hence, there is still room for WIMBY-SF to be improved in the coming months. Considering the SF coverage, the WIMBY-SF implementation also overlaps over 95% of the WindPRO results. The advantages of the WIMBY-SF calculator are its light memory footprint on disk, its easy installation, and the various options for visualisation of results.

The provided data set and the central part of this deliverable include examples of the outputs of the developed tool, which will be key for developing the presentation of impacts in the WIMBY Web-GIS.

In the months ahead, time will be invested in improving the calculation time of the WIMBY-SF tool. Furthermore, we will evaluate how additional factors on SF modelling, especially meteorological information, e.g., wind speed, wind direction and cloud coverage, can be incorporated.

4. Accident risk assessment

4.1 Methodology overview

The methodological framework for accident risk assessment can be categorised into five distinct phases:

1. Compilation of accident database
2. Cross-checking, verification, and update of accident records
3. Consolidation of the accident database
4. Risk assessment of wind power accidents
5. Mapping process and wind power accident tool development

4.2 Compilation of accident database

4.2.1 Data acquisition

Acquiring comprehensive, consistent, and reliable data on accidents in the energy sector is not a trivial task^{16,25}, and especially remains a challenge for wind power, as highlighted by several reports and articles.^{10,35–37} Despite these shortcomings in reporting, limited and scarcely coordinated efforts among various stakeholders and countries have been made to improve the accessibility and transparency of such data. Moreover, manufacturers and operators usually only publish incident data which are mandatory to report; data by national authorities are often not directly comparable and are restricted to summary statistics, and compilations by NGOs and wind power opponents do not follow scientific reporting standards. Therefore, the WIMBY project aims to compile a comprehensive, global data set that uses publicly available data sources and builds upon the established format of the Paul Scherrer Institute's (PSI) ENergy-related Severe Accident Database (ENSAD)^{25,38}.

4.2.2 Primary information sources for wind power accidents

Different organisations collect data on wind power accidents, including industry ³⁷, authorities ³⁹, and independent private organisations that are often opponents of wind power ⁴⁰. The present data collection effort relies on open access data, and therefore, the Scotland against Spin (SaS) data set ⁴¹ has been selected as the starting point.

The SaS data is compiled from official press releases and reports provides a rich and extensive source of information on different types of accidents and their consequences. Furthermore, it includes selected summary reports. The SaS data set has been used in several studies analysing wind power accident risk ^{9,35,42}. In contrast to these studies, we do not use the SaS data immediately for our analysis but start with a thorough verification, harmonisation, and validation process to ensure the highest possible completeness, consistency, and accuracy. Burgherr et al. ²⁸ describe the individual steps of this process, except the most recent updates summarised in this report.

For example, accidents in China appear to be underrepresented in the SaS database, especially considering China's status as a leading country in wind turbine development and deployment. Partially this gap may be due to a language barrier, as most entries in the SaS dataset come from European news websites, reporting primarily in English and other European languages. A complementary approach involved web scraping from regional news sources to overcome this hurdle.

4.2.3 Web-scraping methodology

Web-scraping, natural language processing (NLP) models and related approaches stemming from machine learning and artificial intelligence have been adopted. The screening and selection of reliable Chinese websites reporting wind power accidents was done with the support of a native speaker and expert in energy systems analysis at PSI. In the end, only one website ⁴³ was considered, underscoring the challenge of obtaining comprehensive data at the global level.

The applied web scraping and information retrieval approach aims to extract as much information as possible from each article to ensure a thorough representation of wind turbine accidents in the Chinese context because of the previously identified indications for underreporting (compare section 4.2.2). This includes details about the type of accident,

date of occurrence, specific location, types of consequences and their severity, and any other helpful information.

The actual data extraction process can be split into three basic steps:

- Link Navigation: systematically explore each link from the identified sources, relying on the accident category designated by the website for relevant articles on wind turbine incidents.
- Information translation and extraction: for each relevant article, essential details such as title, publication date, and article text are extracted and translated from Chinese to English for further analysis.
- Use of machine learning models: a general-purpose machine learning model (ChatGPT) is used to process the extracted text and identify key data entries related to wind turbine accidents. This approach increases the efficiency and accuracy of information extraction.

4.2.4 Windfarm and wind turbine datasets

Another limitation of publicly available accident reports, and articles is that they often do not provide technical details on the involved and affected wind turbines and wind farms. For this purpose, the compiled wind power accident database was complemented and combined (i.e., interlinked) with two additional datasets. This allowed us to fill in missing information in individual accident database entries and to overlay the actual accident and risk indicator maps with additional information layers.

Specifically, two datasets from Wind Power were used ⁴⁴. These datasets provide crucial information on wind farms and individual turbines, including commissioning dates, locations, power capacities, number of turbines, turbine types, manufacturer details, and hub height. These datasets were also used to improve geo-referencing of accident locations, which is fundamental for the envisaged mapping tool to visualize spatially resolved risk indicators.

The wind farm dataset includes critical details such as commissioning date, exact location, power capacity, number of turbines, and specific turbine types. It provides a comprehensive overview of the wind energy infrastructure and its characteristics, allowing for a more nuanced analysis of the relationships between these characteristics and accident occurrences.

The wind turbine dataset provides information on the manufacturer, hub height, and potentially other technical specifications. It contributes to a deeper understanding of the technological aspects of the wind turbines in the study regions, which is essential when assessing the potential causes and consequences of accidents.

Despite the information available in these additional datasets, there are challenges in integrating them with the wind power accident database described before. In several cases the specific location and turbine type are not sufficiently detailed in the accident reports and, therefore, a straightforward linking of data records may not be feasible with the wind farm and wind turbine datasets. Several approaches to overcoming this problem are discussed in the methodology chapter, including the adoption of standard identifiers or location-based matching allowing to link accident reports to corresponding wind farm and turbine characteristics.

4.3 Cross-checking, verification, and update of accident records

First, the individual accident records were checked for completeness and consistency. The raw dataset (i.e., SaS and additional sources) comprised 3,338 entries covering the period from 1980 to June 2022. Another update until the end of 2023 will be carried out in the first half of 2024 when more recent data have become available. During the verification and consolidation process, 354 entries were removed because they did not report specific events, providing a general overview of wind power accidents and their impacts instead. Furthermore, 111 duplicate entries were identified and excluded since the SaS produces separate entries for accidents with multiple consequences (e.g., fatalities and injured persons), although they are concerned with the same accident.

Moreover, the years between 1980–1999 were excluded from the final dataset used for analysis, mainly due to the low relevance in terms of numbers and severity in such a large timespan: in the 1980s, only ten accidents were reported, of which eight occurred in the USA and two in Denmark. In the 1990s, annual accidents increased but were still significantly lower than those occurring from the 2000s onward, and no offshore accidents had been reported. The final dataset from January 2000 to June 2022 consisted of 2,770 accident records, ensuring a consistent and representative compilation.

4.4 Consolidation of the accident database

The initial consolidation of the final dataset included several harmonisation steps such as standardisation of location names (i.e., site/area, country), addition of new fields (e.g., On/Offshore, country group, etc.) to allow sorting and filtering as well as to ensure a detailed representation of human health and environmental impacts, accident types and life-cycle phases. For a more detailed description, see Burgherr et al. ²⁸.

4.4.1 Geo-referencing of accidents

Accurate geo-referencing is necessary to place accidents on a map, i.e., translating the location description into geographic coordinates. This is accomplished by linking the wind farm identified in the accident report to the corresponding entry in the wind farm dataset, whose coordinates were then used. It should be noted that the country where an accident occurred is specified for most accidents. Still, the precision of the actual location can vary substantially, ranging between a specific wind farm location and the indication of a municipality or more generic levels (e.g., region, state, etc.). In some instances, no location information is provided at all. To determine the most appropriate match for a location description, a wind farm accuracy scoring system was developed and applied to identify the most likely wind farm for each accident. This followed the spatial classification used in the wind farm dataset (see section 4.2.4), based on the five categories, namely country, state, area, city, and wind farm.

For the preliminary map, only accidents with known wind farm details were included to increase the confidence in the accuracy of the map. However, the geo-referencing will be supplemented with additional information for the remaining accidents. In cases where the automatic procedure still does not yield sufficient results, it will be further investigated manually. At this stage, different accuracy levels will be indicated, including individual wind farms, local administrative areas (e.g., commune, municipality), small regions (NUTS 3), basic regions (NUTS 3), major socio-economic regions (NUTS 1), and country.

4.5 Risk assessment of wind power accidents

First, the final accident data set from Jan 2000 to Jun 2022 was analysed regarding temporal trends in the numbers of accidents, fatalities, and injuries. Second, accident data were evaluated for different attributes such

as country, type of accident, environmental impact, and life cycle phase. Third, risk indicators were calculated for three countries: OECD (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development), non-OECD and EU27 (excluding the UK). These aggregated indicators determine the extent of expected risk, whereas maximum consequences proxy for risk aversion.²⁵ The preliminary results focus on fatalities, but corresponding injury indicators will be calculated for the final version of this deliverable.

Fatality rates were normalised per electricity generation unit (i.e., Gigawatt-electric-year, GWeyr) to ensure direct comparisons between country groups and corresponding onshore and offshore accidents. Fatality rates were computed for all fatal accidents (≥ 1 fatality). Still, the so-called severe fatality rates were calculated, which only included accidents with at least five deaths⁴⁵. The maximum consequences indicator refers to the deadliest single accident of a given country group during the observation period for onshore and offshore events, respectively. An overview of preliminary accident risk results is available in Burgherr et al.²⁸

In the next stage, the risk indicators for country groups will be disaggregated, which is a prerequisite for calculating and generating accident risk maps at high spatial resolution in the WIMBY project.

4.6 Mapping process and wind power accident tool development

The geospatial visualisation of wind farm accidents was achieved using the Folium package in Python. Folium is a Python library for interactive maps based on the Leaflet JavaScript library and integrates with OpenStreetMap data, offering a robust mapping and visualisation solution.

Folium enables the creation of dynamic markers on the map, each representing a separate accident. Close accidents are grouped intelligently when zoomed out for a more compact view. The markers are colour-coded according to the accident's severity, yielding a perceptive and interactive representation of the spatial pattern of wind farm accidents.

Using OpenStreetMap, wind farm accidents were plotted according to their latitude and longitude coordinates. This served as a basis for incorporating further features and gaining insights into these incidents' spatial distribution and characteristics (Figure 8). The upper map (panel a) provides an overview of Europe, while the lower map (panel b) showcases a zoom-in and the available information for a specific accident as a pop-up. Details on the availability of the accident map is available in the Annex. Finally, it

should be noted that the map is restricted to Europe as this is the focus in the WIMBY project, whereas the complete accident database has a global coverage.

Figure 8 Wind power accident mapping tool: panel a (top) provides an overview of Europe, and panel b (bottom) shows a zoom-in and the display of accident-specific information in a pop-up window.

The following features were included in this first version of the wind power mapping tool:

1. **Marker Size Calculation Function:** A function was designed to determine the marker size on the map according to accident severity (i.e., fatalities and injuries). The marker size is adjusted dynamically based on severity using a multiplier. It should be noted that when points are clustered, the size is constant, but a number inside the marker reveals the number of accidents for clarity.
2. **Marker Placement:** A Folium CircleMarker was added to the map for each accident record. The marker's location corresponds to the wind farm's geographical coordinates (see section 3.2 for accuracy discussion).
3. **Popup Information:** For each marker, a popup window displays relevant information about the accident, including its ID, type, fatalities, injuries, date, and the associated wind farm.
4. **Marker Color Coding:** The color of the markers was based on the accident's severity. Red markers represent accidents with fatalities, and blue markers indicate accidents with injuries, and green markers denote accidents with no fatalities or injuries. When accidents are grouped, this is characterised by a yellow marker.
5. **Marker Clustering:** The markers were added to a marker cluster for improved map readability, mainly when dealing with many data points.

This visualisation approach offers an interactive and geospatial understanding of wind farm accidents. The color-coded and size-adjusted markers provide a quick overview of each incident's severity, enhancing the map's interpretability.

4.7 Conclusions

A comprehensive framework for risk assessment of wind power accidents has been proposed and implemented. In particular, it was demonstrated

that publicly available information on wind power accidents can provide a rich data source. However, to reach a comparable level of completeness and detail as the authoritative ENSAD database, substantial verification, cross-checking, and harmonisation efforts need to be carried out because public data sources usually do not follow scientific standards, and to ensure that accident data can be combined with other data sources (e.g., wind farm and turbine data). The compiled data set offers a basis for diverse analyses ranging from simple summary statistics and accident characterisation to temporal and spatial trends, evaluation of patterns for selected attributes aggregated normalised risk indicators, and wind power accident mapping tool for visual representation of accidents and risk indicators at high spatial resolution, which ultimately will be incorporated in the WIMBY toolbox. In conclusion, this analysis provides the foundation for a transparent, data-driven dialogue with stakeholders to smoothen public acceptance and reduce societal risks.

4.7.1 Future work and enhancements

- Development of a standardised workflow of the proposed methodological approach in a Jupyter notebook to automate future updates of the wind power accident database and associated risk calculations and aggregated risk indicators.
- Optionally, it could be explored if health impacts due to accidents could be converted to a common unit (e.g., Years of Life Lost (YOLL) or Disability Adjusted Life Years (DALY)) to enable a direct comparison with noise and shadow flicker impacts.
- Calculate spatially disaggregated risk indicators to generate a high-resolution wind power accident risk map at the European scale.
- Enrich the accident risk mapping tool with additional data layers.
- Integrate the accident risk mapping tool in the WIMBY toolbox.

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ANNEX

Lden_map_Switzerland_2023-12-04.html: map of wind turbine installations in Switzerland and population exposed to noise emissions.

wind_turbine_accidents_map_europe.html: map of wind turbine accidents in Europe.

SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_10_3_1_2,
SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_20_7_1_3,
SFraster_multi_53.123084_5.588264_30_14_1_4,
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_10_3_1_2,
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_20_7_1_3,
SFvec_multi_53.123084_5.588264_30_14_1_4: Shadow flicker example calculations

